

Research on the problems and countermeasures in the construction of Chinese corporate culture: Take FAW Group Corporation as an example

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Abstract

With the continuous development and improvement of China's market economy, in addition to production, the competition among enterprises has begun to be more obvious at the cultural level. This kind of enterprise characteristic is for enterprises to provide sufficient enterprise competitiveness in the market environment of rapid economic development in the new era and the tide of enterprise system reform, and it is also the basic condition for the enterprise leadership to formulate sustainable development for enterprises. Based on the current situation of the development of FAW Group's corporate culture, this paper further sorts out the context of FAW Group's corporate culture development through objective and systematic analysis of the evolution of FAW Group's corporate culture at four different stages of development, points out the new direction of FAW Group's corporate culture construction and the new problems that need to be solved through the analysis of the existing problems and causes in the development of FAW Group's corporate culture, and conducts research on the countermeasures for the in-depth cultivation of FAW Group's corporate culture. It further clarifies the analysis of FAW Group's corporate culture development strategy in the new era, the core elements of FAW Group's corporate culture in-depth cultivation in the new era and implementation countermeasures and provides reference significance and role for FAW Group's corporate culture construction.

Keywords: Corporate culture; FAW Group; Institution-building; Issue; Countermeasures.

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Introduction

With the continuous development of our country, our market economy is also constantly progressing. In this context, China's enterprises are facing huge market competition challenges while ushering in a period of development opportunities. Only by continuously improving their management and production levels can enterprises gain a place in the increasingly fierce market competition. At the same time, enterprises also need to pay more attention to the construction and improvement of corporate culture, making it an important soft power for enterprise development, making enterprises more cohesive, and providing effective spiritual support for the development of enterprises. From the current point of view, the competition between enterprises is becoming increasingly fierce, and it has developed from simple product competition to comprehensive competition, and cultural competition has become an important content of enterprise development. In the current increasingly severe development situation, corporate culture construction is an important foundation for the long-term development of enterprises. Corporate culture construction can better unite enterprise employees so that the enterprise truly becomes an organic, unified whole, all employees tightly condensed together so that each other promotes each other, so that employees form a strong cohesion and inject greater strength into the development of enterprises, so as to effectively

promote the development of enterprises. On the basis of the continuous development and improvement of China's market economy, enterprises need to face greater competitive pressure from the market and foreign enterprises. Therefore, enterprises need to take all favorable means to continuously improve their economic performance and cultural strength and better enhance their market competitiveness by creating a systematic and perfect cultural system so that enterprises have better cultural support. In this context, this paper takes this as the starting point, combined with the development status of FAW Group enterprises in China, conducts in-depth research on the actual situation of its current cultural construction, conducts in-depth research on the lessons learned and existing problems in the process of its cultural construction, and then puts forward effective countermeasures on this basis, hoping to provide useful help for the development of FAW Group enterprises and also provide effective support for the development and progress of other state-owned enterprises.

The purpose of this study is to analyze and study the process of accumulation, precipitation, and construction of the corporate culture of FAW Group in combination with the process of modernization of China's market economy and enterprise management practice, draw on foreign theories and methods on enterprise culture research and analysis, explore the corporate culture construction and cultivation mode and corporate culture management ideas of state-owned enterprises with Chinese characteristics with practical significance, and analyze the corporate culture construction of FAW Group and many domestic enterprises. The in-depth cultivation and research of corporate culture will surely provide a highly targeted and valuable operation mode and construction direction. As a representative of state-owned enterprises, FAW Group's experience in corporate culture construction has certain reference significance for the corporate culture construction of state-owned enterprises in China, so this paper aims to study the corporate culture construction path of FAW Group and explore a new model of corporate culture construction in state-owned enterprises. Focusing on the research on corporate culture of FAW Group, this paper expounds the connotation of corporate culture as the spiritual wealth and material form with the characteristics of the enterprise created in the production, operation, and management activities of enterprises under certain social history, economic, and cultural conditions, and puts forward the direction and ideas of corporate culture construction and the mode of corporate culture construction of state-owned enterprises according to the characteristics and realities of state-owned enterprises.

Today, when the development of China's modern enterprise system is becoming more developed, FAW Group combines the needs of enterprise development with the national development planning and policy tendency. On the basis of inheriting the original corporate culture, it should keep pace with the times to enrich the corporate culture of the unit, giving it a new era connotation and historical significance. The research of this paper can match the corporate culture with the medium and long-term development goals of FAW Group from the actual development of the enterprise and promote the cultivation of the corporate culture in the new era. Improving the corporate culture awareness of the leaders and employees of state-owned enterprises, optimizing the modern management structure of enterprises, and improving the ideological and political work of enterprises can help FAW Group improve the internal cohesion of enterprises and cultivate high-quality human resources, which is of certain practical significance for improving the internal core competitiveness and enterprise management level of FAW Group.

Literature Review

Corporate Culture

Corporate culture is a broad and abstract management concept that is both virtual and real. Since the 1970s, Western businesses and management circles have begun to conduct systematic research on corporate culture. Since then, the objective phenomenon and fact of corporate culture have been gradually raised to the theoretical level to understand, analyze and research, and a new management ideology and cultural awareness have been formed based on the foundation of enterprise management and centered on

people. Deal and Kennedy (1982) systematically discuss corporate culture, which collects and summarizes a large number of rich pieces of information from hundreds of enterprises in the United States, analyzes the core elements and formation process of American corporate culture, prompts the success secrets of many famous large companies, and immediately spreads to all over the world. With a profound influence, enterprises from all over the world have set off a “cultural fever.” Taylor (1992) defined culture as follows: “*Culture or civilization is a complex whole of knowledge, beliefs, arts, moral laws, laws, customs, and other abilities and habits acquired by people who are members of society.*” This definition is already relatively authoritative. Based on this, we define culture as the sum of the spiritual and material outcomes of the interaction between people and the environment. This can include lifestyles, life values, knowledge, technological achievements, and all material objects that have been transformed by people and have human characteristics.

American scholars John Kotter and James Heskett (2011) believe that corporate culture refers to the corporate values owned by employees of an enterprise and the common cultural phenomena shared by different geographical environment departments (as cited by Karpenko & Basenko, 2017). Jack Welch, an expert in contemporary international management, said that corporate culture is the ultimate driving force for maintaining productivity growth, and it is also the source of power without limits. Corporate culture is a new modern enterprise management theory and a sign of enterprise maturity. Corporate culture and economic ethics are becoming key factors in the rise and fall of enterprises. Excellent corporate culture can enhance cohesion and centripetal force internally, establish an image externally, expand market influence, and is an important part of the core competitiveness of enterprises. A first-class enterprise must have an excellent corporate culture. This has become a general consensus among foreign enterprises and management. In order for enterprises to truly gain an invincible position in the market and build an evergreen foundation, they must cultivate and deepen the construction of corporate culture (Grant, 2017).

Since about 1984, foreign corporate culture theory has been introduced into China and has received increased attention from the business community and academia, especially in recent years. A new round of corporate culture fever has been formed, and Chinese enterprises have successively increased investment in corporate culture construction and received results. From the current point of view, China attaches great importance to the relevant issues of corporate culture construction, so it has also conducted in-depth research. Chinese scholars have discussed the relevant content of corporate culture construction by adopting a series of research methods and seeking improvement strategies for corporate culture construction through a series of problems that hinder the development of enterprises in the process of corporate culture construction. Although the development momentum of China's state-owned enterprises has been relatively good in recent years, on the whole, many state-owned enterprises lack culture, cultural fault lines are relatively serious, and the construction of enterprise culture lacks the guidance of systematic theory (Holz, 2019). Through research on a number of enterprises and interviews with enterprise managers, many enterprises lack innovation awareness in the construction of corporate culture (Sun, 2020).

After investigating a number of large state-owned enterprises, the factors restricting the development of state-owned enterprise culture are: the construction of corporate culture lacks strategic awareness and cannot provide guidance for the production and operation activities of enterprises; weak innovation ability of enterprises; lack of corresponding technical management talents, resulting in slow construction of corporate culture; enterprises lack a sense of competition and cannot correctly position themselves in the market (Jones & Zou, 2017). Yanyi (2015) pointed out that the construction of state-owned enterprise culture is greatly influenced by national traditional culture. The centralized concept of traditional culture has led to the prevalence of leadership dictatorship in the construction of existing corporate culture, and many things are decided by leaders. The existing institutions are more crowded, and work efficiency is reduced. Many leaders of state-owned enterprises lack a sense of challenge and are unable to conduct bold reforms on the problems existing in the development of enterprises.

Different scholars have views on the concept of corporate culture. The first to define the concept of corporate culture was William Ouchi (1981), who argued that “*traditional customs constitute the culture of a company, and values are also contained in the company's culture.*” O’Reilly et al. (2014) believe that corporate culture is a value shared by all members of the enterprise; this concept is an internalized normative belief that can play an effective role in guiding the behavior of enterprise employees. Schein (2012) mentioned that corporate culture is the enterprise as an organizational form of the process of norms and unique values, business philosophy, organizational atmosphere, and employee emotions. On the whole, corporate culture is a set of concept systems formed by a company and an enterprise in actual production and operation activities, shared and jointly held by all employees, with the values, norms, and business concepts of the organization as the core. These concepts are reflected in the production practices of the enterprise as well as the mental state and way of doing things of the employees. Corporate culture often represents an enterprise; corporate culture can improve the competitiveness of enterprises. Corporate culture contains many aspects, such as business philosophy. The values of an enterprise affect the behavior and thinking mode of employees and are the beliefs shared and recognized by the enterprise and employees. It is necessary to promote the establishment of corporate culture through various activities and corresponding reward mechanisms and to encourage employees to consciously abide by and believe in production and life.

Enterprise Culture Construction

Spiritual culture

For the spiritual culture of enterprises, it is formed in the development process of long-term enterprise production and operation, and the spiritual culture organically formed by the influence of the specific values and thinking modes and behavior patterns of state-owned enterprises is an important core of corporate culture and the superstructure of enterprise development. From the perspective of enterprise values, it refers to the value cognition of enterprise leaders and all employees in the daily production and operation activities of the enterprise; corporate ethics refers to the code of conduct and behavior of the enterprise, mainly used to regulate various relationships; corporate ethics is not mandatory, but the system of the enterprise has strong mandatory characteristics.

Material culture

Corporate material culture refers to the process of daily production and management activities by the employees of the enterprise during the work of the products and services and other forms as the carrier. Effective integration and unified formation of the cultural collective name is an important carrier of corporate culture to be expressed but also an important condition for the shaping and formation of corporate culture and institutional culture. For the employees of the enterprise, the material culture of the enterprise is the cultural product of the enterprise that can be directly perceived. Corporate material culture includes corporate image, corporate environment, and corporate facilities.

Institutional culture

Enterprise institutional culture refers to the expression of institutional carrier culture that has a certain binding and normative effect on all employees of the enterprise. It can be said that it is the mandatory norms and guidelines followed by all employees of the enterprise after a long period of production and operation management practice; specifically, it is mainly manifested as the following points: first, the general system. It refers to the universally binding responsibility system, management system, and work system promulgated and implemented by enterprises. These systems have a good binding force on the internal enterprise and are the cultural carriers with written forms within the enterprise, such as production, equipment, finance, manpower and other management systems, and reward and punishment assessment systems. The second is the special regime. Special systems are generally manifested as non-procedural

systems, such as the summary and commendation meeting system, the employee review cadre system, etc. Finally, there are corporate customs, which refer to the rituals, festivals, activities, and other forms that have been inherited and established by enterprises for a long time.

Current Situation of FAW Group Corporation's Corporate Culture Construction

FAW Group Corporation is referred to as FAW, and its corporate brand is FAW. In 1953, the First Automobile Manufacturing Plant broke ground on the land of Changchun, and the automobile industry of New China began here. Since then, FAW people have begun an epic development process. In the process of FAW's first entrepreneurship, all FAW people carried forward the spirit of hard work and entrepreneurship and built and put into operation in three years, ending the history of New China not being able to produce automobiles. In the process of FAW's second entrepreneurship, FAW embarked on a new road of enterprise development under the premise of "non-stop production and no production reduction." In the process of FAW's third venture, FAW carried forward the enterprise spirit of "learning, innovation, struggle, and self-improvement" and established a wide range of products covering medium, heavy, light, car, passenger, and micro products. FAW has produced and sold more than 16 million vehicles of various types, paid more than 200 billion yuan in profits and taxes, and established a nationwide automobile network. While consolidating and developing the domestic market, FAW has also continuously developed the international market and initially established a global marketing and procurement system (Feng, 2018; Nam, 2015).

FAW's production enterprises, including wholly owned subsidiaries, holding subsidiaries, and scientific research institutes, are widely distributed in 13 provinces, municipalities, and autonomous regions across the country. Now it has formed an enterprise development pattern extending from the hinterland of Northeast China, covering Bohai Bay, Jiaodong Bay, Guangxi, Yunnan, and Sichuan, forming three main production bases in the southwest, northeast, and Jiaodong, and the enterprise has formed a production of a wide range of trucks, cars, buses, and other complete vehicles, automobile hosts, and auto parts. At present, FAW Group has eight vehicle manufacturers, including Jiefang Company, Car Stock Branch, Bus Co., Ltd., FAW-GM Commercial Light Vehicle Company, and FAW-Volkswagen Company. FAW's vehicle products mainly include: Jiefang brand trucks, Hongqi cars, Besturn cars, FAW-Volkswagen brand Sagitar cars, Magotan cars, Jetta cars, Bora cars, Golf cars, Audi cars, FAW Mazda cars, and FAW Toyota Land Cool Luze multi-functional sports vehicles. FAW's production, sales, and operating income rank at the forefront of China's automotive industry.

FAW Group Corporation was in its embryonic period from the beginning of its establishment to China's reform and opening up. At this stage of development, FAW Group attaches great importance to cultivating the patriotic spirit and collective spirit of the enterprise, and its cultural construction has been greatly influenced by the Soviet management model. Under the guidance of the goal of actively building the basic system of the new Chinese automobile industry, it effectively carries out entrepreneurship and actively establishes the quality culture concept of "*FAW Automobile, Quality First.*" However, during this period, FAW Group did not establish a clear and perfect management concept, and its cultural construction characteristics were spontaneously formed.

The second stage was from the early stage of reform and opening up to around 2000, and the first stage was an important period of growth for FAW Group's corporate culture. In this stage of development, China's market economy system is increasingly perfect, and at this time, the automobile production industry has also developed rapidly. FAW Group Corporation has also begun to recognize the importance of corporate culture, actively build corporate culture, and actively build a business model that is compatible with the market economy system. At the same time, FAW Group also actively borrows and absorbs the management concepts and cultural ideas of foreign enterprises, which it then effectively combines with its

own enterprise development characteristics and gradually forms the corporate culture concept of FAW Group with modern characteristics. In this context, FAW Group's corporate culture attaches importance to production and service, attaches importance to market competition, actively strengthens market awareness, strives to improve the quality of production generated by enterprises, and regards customers as an important concept of enterprise development. In addition, FAW Group has actively innovated its own management system, actively cultivated outstanding talents, attached importance to the establishment of an effective incentive mechanism, and achieved remarkable results. However, in the first delivery stage, FAW Group is affected by some objective factors, such as economic development level and regional differences, and there are still many problems in its business philosophy and management style, as well as problems of incoordination. In general, at this stage, FAW Group's business philosophy, cultural ideas, and value standards have been effectively developed and have become an indispensable and important part and foundation for enterprise development, and its cultural concept construction is constantly improving and developing and gradually realizing formalization, systematization, and institutionalization.

The third stage is from 2000 up to present, which is the mature development stage of FAW Group's cultural construction. FAW Group attaches great importance to the integration of the culture of its subordinate units, and after continuous exploration and improvement, FAW Group has formed a cultural system suitable for the company's own development, such as the spirit of "positive and enterprising, aiming to surpass." Under the guidance of effective cultural thinking, FAW Group Corporation has forged ahead with determination and continuous development, realized the effective improvement of cultural management, and developed an important path for the gradual integration of culture management. At this stage, with cultural development as the carrier, we actively build an enterprise management system and organically combine the two to form a rather colorful cultural system. FAW Group has developed to a large extent thanks to the guidance of its cultural ideas, and with the continuous development and changes of China's economic production environment, FAW Group Corporation still continues to develop and improve its own cultural system and actively innovates its corporate culture system so as to provide more effective support for the future development of the enterprise.

FAW Car conforms to the general trend of the development of the times, firmly grasps the general trend of economic globalization, faces the inner expectations of employees, that is, the demands of designing and manufacturing cars belonging to FAW Car's independent property rights, highlights cultural guidance, carries out full-coverage publicity throughout the company, highlights the individual role of each position, forms a joint force for innovation of the whole system, creates a cultural atmosphere that encourages innovation for everyone, and makes every effort to fight the innovation battle of independent brands. Independent innovation puts culture first; independent development puts culture first. FAW Car takes building the best car, making driving happier, making employees happier, and making society more harmonious as its corporate mission, achieving first-class brands and becoming an internationally competitive automobile enterprise as its corporate vision, striving for the first, innovating the industry, and taking responsibility as the basic understanding of the enterprise spirit for all employees, and the new generation of enterprise spirit of loyalty to the country, self-improvement in market competition, learning from all strong people, and pursuing innovation in all work, FAW Car's personalized corporate culture acts on the corporate strategy to drive strategic realization.

With the advent of the new era, according to the national policy changes, the reform and opening up, and the formulation of the socialist market economy with Chinese characteristics, FAW Group Corporation has also undergone great changes. In order to adapt to market demand and improve the technology and strength of the enterprise, FAW Group Corporation began to establish a corporate culture of "learning, innovation, resistance, and self-improvement". FAW improves the quality of the enterprise by establishing joint venture brands and joint production, and it learns the R&D, production, and marketing technology of world-renowned automobile enterprises through the establishment of FAW-Volkswagen, FAW Audi, and FAW Toyota, joint ventures with Toyota Motor Corporation and Mazda Motor Company

to rapidly improve enterprise hard metrics and to narrow the gap with world-renowned car companies and integrate with the world's automotive industry. Through the technology learned from the joint venture production of world-renowned automobile enterprises, we have successfully developed many new technologies with independent intellectual property rights that are in line with the level of the world automobile industry, such as 6.0V12 engines, 4.8 and 4.0 V8 engines, 3.0V6 engines, and 2.0L4 engines with independent intellectual property rights. Through the improvement of technology, FAW Group has established many subsidiaries and holding companies represented by FAW Car, FAW Dalian (bus), Wuxi Diesel Engine Plant, and Foundry Corporation, which play a decisive role in the development of FAW Group under the market economy system. With the development of the market economy system, FAW Group has also formed a corporate culture suitable for the development of enterprises under the market economy system in the new era.

Methodology

Through reviewing a large number of literature materials, the feasibility of this study was discussed, and the relevant problems and feasibility suggestions of corporate culture construction were collected and sorted out through libraries, bookstores, and databases, particularly in CNKI, which provided feasibility for this study. With the analysis of the universal characteristics of corporate culture construction combined with the comparison of relevant contents in the process of cultural construction at FAW Factory, the problems existing in the process of cultural construction at state-owned enterprises represented by FAW Group are sought. Taking FAW Group's corporate culture construction as the focus of research, the questionnaire was designed to collect data by issuing questionnaires to FAW Group employees, analyze the shortcomings of FAW Group's corporate culture construction, and propose solutions for FAW Group's corporate culture construction, so as to find the general experience of enterprises in cultural construction.

Results and Discussion

In order to explore the problems existing in the construction of FAW Group's corporate culture, the author designed a questionnaire to survey FAW Group employees, covering departments such as technology, sales, and R&D, as well as managers and grassroots employees. This questionnaire was distributed in 100 copies, and the questions mainly focused on the effectiveness of corporate culture construction, employees' understanding of corporate culture, and the development and expression of corporate culture. Based on the analysis of the results of the questionnaire survey, this paper puts forward the following views.

The disconnect between the construction of corporate culture and operation and management

The construction of corporate culture can enhance the cohesion within the enterprise, and the foundation of the construction of corporate culture is to improve the operation and management of the enterprise and promote the development of the enterprise through the corporate culture. In response to this, the questionnaire determines the connection between employees' job work and corporate culture, and the results are shown in the following table:

Table 1. Relevance of culture to their jobs

Issue	How relevant do you think the culture is to your job?			
	Highly relevant	There is a little correlation	Basically irrelevant	There is no contact
Options				
Quantity	24	22	28	26

According to the survey results, 46 out of 100 employees believe that corporate culture affects work motivation and work efficiency, and most of these employees are 40 older employees over the age of the year, while younger employees mostly chose “no contact”. The development of enterprises needs to keep pace with the times; young talents are the driving force of enterprise development, and the concept and awareness of young employees often affect the development direction of enterprises. The younger technical personnel and the concentration of innovation ability reflect the problem that FAW Auto has: a disconnect between corporate culture, construction, operation, and management. FAW Automobile Group employees do not have a good understanding of corporate culture, which can also be reflected in the questionnaire.

Table 2. Company’s corporate culture reflected in different aspects

Issue	Do you think the company’s corporate culture is reflected in?			
	Corporate activities	Slogan atmosphere	Institutional norms	Business activities
Options				
Quantity	12	71	11	6

The 71 employees’ perception of corporate culture is stuck in a “slogan atmosphere”, which highlights the problem that FAW Automobile Group’s corporate culture is out of touch with reality and corporate needs. Although FAW Automobile Group has put forward the corporate tenet of leading technology and caring for customers, among the employees at the grassroots level, some employees who do not have the requirements of science and technology positions and customer service businesses do not know how to practice this purpose in their positions.

The behavioral transformation effect of corporate culture is not good

Corporate culture can guide the behavior of employees. To achieve a win-win situation between enterprises and employees with the fit of individual employees and the enterprise as a whole, FAW Automobile Group has a long history of corporate culture construction, and in the market environment, corporate culture cannot deviate from the needs of employees. "Shout slogans, do face" superstructure cannot improve output. In this regard, the questionnaire considers employees’ awareness of corporate culture and the creation of an atmosphere for corporate culture learning. The following table shows the details:

Table 3. Company’s corporate development purpose

Issue	Do you understand the company’s corporate development purpose?		
	Can understand	Have a basic understanding	Do not understand
Options			
Quantity	67	12	11

As far as FAW Automobile Group's corporate construction and development tenet of “market-oriented, innovation first, knowledge-based, and talent-rooted” is concerned, the awareness rate of employees has reached 80%. It can be said that the corporate culture is basically “well-known” in FAW Automobile Group, but there is still a lot of work to be implemented, from the promotion of the corporate culture concept to the consensus of employee behavior. In the construction of corporate culture, FAW has the problem of internalizing corporate culture into the conscious behavior of employees.

Table 4. Role of corporate culture in their current work

Issue	What do you think is the role of corporate culture in your current work?			
	Guide work and improve efficiency	Understand institutional changes	Relieves work stress	It does not work
Options				
Quantity	39	22	7	32

In the survey of willingness to guide work with corporate culture, only 39 people chose to “improve work efficiency with corporate culture as the core.” According to the survey results, employees generally believe that FAW Group's corporate culture plays a role in the development and implementation of corporate development and strategy and does not play a significant role with individual employees. In the questionnaire survey, the concept of “FAW people” was separated from the cognition of “FAW employees,” and corporate visions such as technology and market were not effectively linked to the interests of employees, resulting in insufficient motivation in corporate culture.

The implementation of enterprise culture construction lags behind

Institutional culture is an important part of corporate culture construction, and corporate culture construction is inseparable from the guarantee of the system. Corporate culture landing is not only for the majority of employees on the FAW Group corporate culture value concept of the cognitive process but also for the establishment of corporate culture system important measures. The implementation of corporate culture construction is first of all a communication process uploaded and issued. In this regard, FAW Automobile Group's survey results are as follows:

Table 5. Information about company systems

Issue	The way you get information about company systems is:			
	Document transmission	Colleague notification	Internal communication	Information sharing
Quantity	37	30	11	22

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Among the 100 respondents, 67 obtained information on FAW’s corporate group system through document transmission and colleague notification, and 33 chose information sharing and internal communication. This also shows that there is a time difference in the establishment and establishment of corporate culture, and the construction of corporate culture is the ideological and behavioral style construction of the enterprise workforce, which ultimately focuses on business management and products, brand image, and competitiveness. The lack of unity of systems and concepts and the mismatch between management and cultural construction are all reasons for this problem. Taking the implementation process of FAW Automobile Group’s corporate culture as an example, the enterprise put forward the enterprise spirit of being rigorous, innovative, collaborative, and practical as the spiritual indicator of employee behavior standards and guidelines, implemented the cultural manual refined and summarized by the management department, and posted slogans, but the implementation of these terms into the work requirements is not clear. We can see one or two things from the results of the questionnaire.

Table 6. Company’s corporate development purpose

Issue	Do you think the current corporate system matches the corporate culture?		
	High degree of matching	Basic matching	Does not match
Quantity	37	30	11

In the survey, more than 80% of employees believed that the corporate system did not match the corporate culture well; in fact, FAW Group's implementation of rigorous and practical work specifications and a work assessment system was not related to market demand or enterprise demand. In order for enterprises to achieve innovation, what they need is the introduction of a large number of technical talents, the establishment of a technological innovation incentive mechanism, and the transformation of their strategic perspective.

FAW Group's Corporate Culture Construction Strategy

1. Promote the coordination and unity of corporate culture and development strategy

In the process of building corporate culture, FAW Automobile Group should take the company's development strategy as the basis. There must be no contradiction between social culture and the construction of enterprises, so that the cultural construction of enterprises serves the development of enterprises and conforms to the connotation and mainstream direction of socialist culture. Using the strategy of the enterprise will guide the cultural construction of the enterprise, and the corporate culture promotes the implementation and implementation of the strategy. The two form a virtuous circle, promote each other, and realize the coordination and unity of the corporate culture and corporate strategy. The senior management of the enterprise should take a long-term view and put the cultural construction of the enterprise as an important link to the development of the enterprise, making it a virtuous circle. The achievements of FAW Automobile Group in promoting the construction of corporate culture will inevitably have a positive impact on the company's development strategy. The benign development of enterprises requires the joint efforts of many links and factors. Enterprises are organizations that pursue economic profits but cannot blindly pursue economic interests and ignore social benefits. FAW Automobile Group should use the construction of corporate culture to strengthen the collective sense of honor and disgrace and the common sense of struggle and coordinate the relationship between departments and employees. In order to achieve rational and scientific management, it is necessary to gradually form an organizational and management structure that conforms to the characteristics of enterprise development, which is also the direction of modern enterprise operation and management. FAW Automobile Group should also distinguish the job responsibilities of different departments, conduct each work in combination with the company's philosophy and development vision, truly integrate corporate culture into every work of the enterprise, and think and design from the perspective of the long-term development of the enterprise. The group should enrich the expression of corporate culture and guide and standardize the behavior of employees.

2. Establish and improve the employee incentive system to improve the sense of enterprise identity of employees

The employees of the enterprise are the most dynamic factor in the enterprise and the main participants in building the company culture, and the results of development require the active dedication of each one. Therefore, it is necessary to mobilize the enthusiasm and creativity of employees and encourage employees to assume their responsibilities and fulfill their obligations. Departments and employees at all levels should find their position in this activity in which all employees of the company participate and actively do their share of responsibilities. Leaders should play a leading role, strictly demand themselves, consciously practice all aspects of corporate culture construction, and actively advocate for employees to exert subjective initiative and contribute ideas to the construction of corporate culture. Infiltrate the corporate culture into the blood of employees so that they can consciously refer to and standardize their own behavior and thinking in daily production and life and contribute their own strength to the development of the company. It is a step-by-step process for developing practice. In this process, both leaders and employees play an important role; leaders are advocates and leaders, and employees are active practitioners. In building its corporate culture, FAW Automobile Group should recognize that this is an activity and task that concerns all employees of the company, so it should clarify its responsibilities and mobilize the

enthusiasm of everyone. In particular, it should strengthen the education of managers at all levels, play a good role model, and implement various policies and measures to improve the behavior of every employee. In the process of transforming corporate culture behavior, FAW Group should achieve both publicity and guidance, unify all employees on all fronts and fields to recognize and recognize in manufacturing, service management, and job practice, regard it as its own code of conduct, and jointly implement the process of compliance. In this process, we must take employees as the carrier object and influence object of corporate culture construction work, so that the majority of employees are affected and educated in participation, develop thinking patterns and behavior habits that are compatible with corporate culture in participation, and finally achieve a high degree of unity between corporate culture concepts and employee behavior patterns.

3. Improve the institutional mechanism for the construction of enterprise culture

First of all, FAW Automobile Group should refine its work objectives and transform the construction of corporate culture into specific work tasks and work requirements, such as clarifying annual business objectives by department and strengthening the supporting assessment system, so as to promote the implementation of corporate culture construction. Secondly, to strengthen the communication between the top and bottom, the construction of corporate culture and the needs of employees, to improve the enthusiasm of employees, and to enhance the competitiveness of enterprises, the system construction should allow employees to participate in the construction of corporate culture, adhere to a people-oriented strategy, and further inspire the spirit so that every employee's thoughts and actions are unified. Third, incentive mechanisms should be established to create a learning atmosphere and supportive environment so that employees can find a sense of belonging and achieve common development between enterprises and employees. For example, establish an employee training system, cooperate with the company's talent planning to clarify the focus and direction of talent cultivation, and improve the credibility of corporate culture through the construction of internal talent teams. In addition, in order to adapt to market changes, managers should also strengthen their management knowledge, learn from and experiment with the business models and advanced concepts of excellent enterprises, and establish an institutional system suitable for FAW in combination with the actual situation. Finally, FAW Automobile Group should take the connotation of corporate culture as the core of incentive to establish and implement the incentive mechanism, so that innovation can flow from belief to action, so that employees and enterprises can profit and benefit from innovation. Incentives need to pay equal attention to material and spiritual aspects, and enterprises should be rich in corporate cultural activities, such as selecting models and conducting cultural exchange activities, so that employees can consciously participate in the construction and development of corporate culture on the basis of understanding corporate culture.

References

- Deal, T. E., & Kennedy, A. A. (1983). Culture: A new look through old lenses. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 19(4), 498-505. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002188638301900411>
- FAW Group. (n.d.). *Company profile*. <http://www.faw.com/fawen/gyjt36/jtg159/jtjj3/index.html>
- Feng, Q. (2018). *Variety of development: Chinese automakers in market reform and globalization*. Palgrave Macmillan. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-5912-4>
- Grant, A. M. (2017). The third 'generation' of workplace coaching: creating a culture of quality conversations. *Coaching: An International Journal of Theory, Research and Practice*, 10(1), 37-53. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17521882.2016.1266005>
- Holz, C. A. (2019). *The unfinished business of state-owned enterprise reform in the People's Republic of China* (CESifo Working Paper No. 7688). <https://www.cesifo.org/en/publications/2019/working-paper/unfinished-business-state-owned-enterprise-reform-peoples-republic>

- Jones, L., & Zou, Y. (2017). Rethinking the role of state-owned enterprises in China's rise. *New Political Economy*, 22(6), 743-760. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13563467.2017.1321625>
- Karpenko, A., & Basenko, K. (2017). Highly effective corporate culture as an instrument of talents' attracting and retaining. *Baltic Journal of Economic Studies*, 3(4), 101-106. <https://doi.org/10.30525/2256-0742/2017-3-4-101-106>
- Kotter, J. P., & Heskott, J. L. (2011). *Corporate culture and performance* (Reprint ed.). Free Press.
- Nam, K. M. (2015). Compact organizational space and technological catch-up: Comparison of China's three leading automotive groups. *Research Policy*, 44(1), 258-272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2014.08.002>
- O'Reilly III, C. A., Caldwell, D. F., Chatman, J. A., & Doerr, B. (2014). The promise and problems of organizational culture: CEO personality, culture, and firm performance. *Group & Organization Management*, 39(6), 595-625. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1059601114550713>
- Ouchi, W. G. (1981). Organizational paradigms: A commentary on Japanese management and Theory Z organizations. *Organizational Dynamics*, 9(4), 36-43. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0090-2616\(81\)90024-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0090-2616(81)90024-3)
- Schein, E. (2012). Corporate culture. In J. Vogelsang, M. Townsend, M. Minahan, D. Jamieson, J. Vogel, A. Viets, C. Royal, & L. Valek (Eds.), *Handbook for strategic HR: Best practices in organization development from the OD Network* (pp. 253-258).
- Sun, X. (2020). Research on the path to enhance core competitiveness of state-owned enterprises for a new era—from the perspective of corporate culture. In S. B. Tsai, K. F. Lee, & W. Sulisz (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Advances in Management Science and Engineering (IC-AMSE 2020)* (pp. 176-180). Atlantis Press. <https://doi.org/10.2991/aebmr.k.200402.030>
- Taylor, C. (1992). Modernity and the rise of the public sphere. *The Tanner Lectures on Human Values*, 14, 205-260. https://tannerlectures.utah.edu/_resources/documents/a-to-z/t/Taylor93.pdf
- Yanyi, S. (2015, March 3). *On the relationship between corporate culture and corporate core competitiveness*. CCID. <https://ccidgroup.com/sddj/info/1013/1875.htm>